

Survival, growth, yield, and yield attributes of rice varieties grown under waterlogged conditions, Calcutta, India.

Variety	Survival (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Days to 50% flowering	Dry matter production (g/m ²)	Panicles/m ²	Spikelets (10 ³ /m ²)	Grains (10 ³ /m ²)	1,000-grain wt (g)
OR143-7	36	2.0	141	766	117	15	12	27
OR117-215	17	2.2	132	600	50	12	10	21
OR330-40-3	80	2.2	118	758	154	17	14	21
Janaki	87	2.1	122	875	200	15	13	21
BIET724	70	3.1	135	1002	172	20	15	26
BIET807	80	3.6	125	1308	200	23	18	24
BIET821	34	2.0	128	725	119	17	11	24
CR292-5258	31	2.2	150	489	144	20	15	18
CR292-7050	21	2.0	150	466	69	8	7	30
CR221-1030	87	3.5	134	792	182	22	19	22
CN499-160-2-1	29	2.2	134	617	126	12	9	18
CN499-160-13-6	83	2.1	135	608	200	21	17	17
CN505-5-32-9	12	1.2	140	325	50	11	8	20
CN506-147-2-1	93	2.4	142	880	200	19	15	25
CN506-147-14-2	14	3.3	135	685	90	19	16	23
PLA1100	12	0.8	144	242	27	7	5	20
NC492	90	4.9	130	1116	253	21	19	31
Tilakkachari	93	3.8	132	1205	255	25	17	26
Mean	53.8	2.5	134.8	747.7	144.9	16.99	13.4	23.02
CD at 5% P	21	0.6	4	200	52	3	3	3

253 panicles. Tilakkachari also produced the maximum spikelets. NC492 yielded highest with 4.9 t/ha, and PLA1100 lowest with 0.80 t/ha. NC492 had high total dry matter, high panicle number, the highest 1,000-grain weight, and high survival percentage. Survival of plants under waterlogged situation is the prime criterion for plant establishment and subsequent manifestation of yield potential. □

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Selection criteria for an F₄ population of a deep water rice cross

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At CRRI we crossed Pankaj, a high yielding semidwarf, with Nagaribao, a traditional deep water rice, to develop high yield deep water lines. Based on their performance, 817 F₃ lines were selected and planted in kharif in inter-

mediate 15-50 cm water depth. Fifty-two plants of each line were planted at 20- × 25-cm spacing, giving an F₄ population of 42,484 plants. The parents also were grown. Deep water killed 1,285 plants in the F₄ population and very wide growth variation was observed among and within lines. Variation was less within lines than between lines.

From 245 lines we selected 980 plants with high vigor; thick to medium-thick culms; compact tillering; rapid internode elongation; nodal rooting; small erect leaves; medium to tall height; lodging

resistance; awnless, nonshattering panicles; dormancy; and good panicle weight. Panicle weight was measured by dividing the total grain weight after removing the chaff by panicle length. We called that ratio C. Plants selected from the field by sight were tested for C factor and those with 0.1 C were judged panicle weight types. Of 980 selected plants, 522 had C 0.1. C is a desirable selection criterion for high yield in segregating generations of deep water crosses. C is 0.06 for deep water Nagaribao and 0.15 for high yielding variety Pankaj. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TEMPERATURE TOLERANCE

Evaluating rices for cold tolerance

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Low temperatures are a major constraint to rice production in the hill region of India, where they adversely affect spring-sown upland rice at germination and early seedling growth, and transplanted rice

during ripening. We screened rices for low temperature tolerance in three experiments.

In the first, 135 varieties from different rice growing regions of the world, including some local hill collections, were evaluated for germination and seedling vigor in the spring of 1981 and 1982. On 2 Mar, 50 seeds of each variety were sown in 2 rows at 2-cm depth. The first seedlings emerged 18 d after sowing. L 62G,

Heug Jodo, Jodo, Heugdo, IRAT102, Khonorullo, K78-28, Daegaldo, Mujudo, and L 62-2A had more than 75% germination at an average 11°C field temperature. Sixty more genotypes emerged at 13°C and the rest emerged when the average temperature rose to 15°C in the first week of Apr. Of the early-emerging genotypes, all but IRAT102, K78-28, and L 62-2A had good seedling vigor at low temperatures and maintained their vigor

until panicle initiation.

Varieties VHC 1253, Lengkwang, Hawang Haedo, VL 206, L 105-8, VLK39, and Himdhan had poor early seedling growth but recovered rapidly when the temperature rose above 25°C. They reached a par in vigor with the earliest varieties in both years.

A similar set of varieties was evaluated

under controlled conditions. Twenty-five seeds of each were placed in petri dishes containing a mixture of sand, soil, and water. The same set of 10 varieties that performed well in the first experiment had more than 80% germination at 11 °C.

The third experiment had 16 varieties planted in pots. At booting stage, one set of pots was transferred to 2,400 m alti-

tude where night temperatures were 10° to 5 °C. Another set was maintained at 1,600 m altitude where night temperatures were 18° to 12 °C. Only L 62G, Khonorullo, L 62-2A, UPRH299, and L 12-1A had good spikelet fertility and leaf color at 2,400 m altitude. Olbyed, Gangweondo, JC99, and Nancee had normal leaf color. □

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Effect of urea foliar spraying on rice tungro virus (RTV) infection

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In Mar-May 1984 there was a severe outbreak of RTV on several rice varieties in North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu. We tested a 1% foliar spraying of urea for RTV control on susceptible IET1722 at different sites. Disease incidence was measured at first spraying (20 d after transplanting [DT] and 20 d before harvest, using the Standard evaluation system for rice.

At first spraying 5-10% RTV infection

Effect of foliar application of urea on RTV infection, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Disease incidence (%)		Mean yield (t/ha)
	20 d after transplanting	20 d before harvest	
1% urea sprayed at 20, 30, 40, and 50 d + phosphamidon (85% EC) at 20 and 35 d after transplanting	7 - 8	7 - 10	4.2
Phosphamidon (85% EC) sprayed at 20 and 35 d after transplanting	6 - 7	38 - 41	2.4
No treatment control	5 - 9	60 - 72	1.2

was recorded. Foliar application of 1% urea at 20, 30, 40, and 50 DT + phosphamidon (85% EC) 320 ml/ha at 20 and 35 DT effectively controlled RTV up to

10% infection. In phosphamidon-treated and control fields, disease spread was 41 and 72% with a corresponding yield reduction (see table). □

New rice grassy stunt virus (GSV) strain in Thailand

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Rice plants with symptoms of an unknown disease and other virus diseases were collected at several sites in Thailand and tested for virus presence by immune electron microscopy (IEM) and the dipping method. For IEM, grids were treated with an antiserum to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) or rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) at 1 : 1000 dilution. After incubation with sap of plant samples, grids were floated on anti-

Table 1. Detection by IEM technique and dipping method of viruses from rice plants with different virus symptoms. ^a

Variety	Symptoms (visual assessment)	Virus particles detected by dipping	Reaction of extracts in IEM to antiserum against	
			RTSV	RTBV
Kaimukdum pl. no. 1	RSV	RSV	-	-
Kaimukdum pl. no. 2	RSV	RSV	-	-
Kaimukdum pl. no. 3	RTV	RTSV	+	-
Kaimukdum pl. no. 4	RTV	RTBV	-	+
Kaimukdum pl. no. 5	RTV	RTSV, RTBV	+	+
Kaimukdum pl. no. 6	RSV	RSV	-	-
Kaimukdum pl. no. 7	RSV, unknown	RSV	-	-
Kaimukdum pl. no. 8	unknown	-	-	-
Apple Thong pl. no. 1	unknown	-	-	-
Apple Thong pl. no. 2	unknown	-	-	-
Number 20 pl. no. 1	unknown	-	-	-
Number 20 pl. no. 2	unknown	-	-	-
Number 20 pl. no. 3	unknown	-	-	-

^a + and - indicate positive and negative reactions. RSV = rice ragged stunt, RTV = rice tungro virus.